

Heat Exchanger and Plug Nozzle Made of Carbon-Carbon Composites to an Engine for a Future Space Vehicle

Hiroshi Hatta*, Masashi Koyama*, Ken Goto*, Y.Kogo**

* Institute of Space and Astronautical Science & The Graduate University for Advanced Studies
3-1-1 Yoshinodai, Sagami-hara, Kanagawa, 229-8510 Japan

** Tokyo University of Science, Department of Material Science and Technology,
Faculty of Industrial Science and Technology,
2641 Yamazaki, Noda, Chiba 278-8510, Japan

ABSTRACT

Feasibility studies were carried out aiming at the application of carbon/carbon (C/C) composites to a turbine disk, heat exchangers, and a plug nozzle for an engine intended for use in a future reusable space vehicle. In these applications, the maximum temperature was estimated to be about 1500 °C. In order to withstand this high temperature, attempts were made to utilize three-dimensionally reinforced C/C composites. The most serious problem encountered in the application of C/Cs to the turbine disk was the loss of fragments of the composite located near the outer periphery due to strong centrifugal force, which resulted in severe vibration due to rotational imbalance. The heat exchangers and plug nozzle have complex shapes in order to realize a large heat exchanging area. Joined structures were explored for these components. The principal effort in these applications has been placed on finding structures requiring low joining strength and developing materials with low gas leakage.

KEYWORDS Carbon/carbon (C/C) composite, Thermo-mechanical properties, Turbine blade, Heat exchangers, High temperature properties, Bonding, Gas leakage

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon-carbon (C/C) composites are attractive materials because of their superior specific strength and specific elastic modulus at elevated temperatures over 2000°C [1-3]. In light of these advantages, many attempts have been made to apply C/C composites to high temperature structures such as space vehicles, hypersonic airplanes, and fusion reactors [1-5]. However, C/C composites have seldom been applied to primary structures requiring high load bearing capability, mainly due to their weakness against high temperature oxidation. Thus, the improvement of oxidation resistance has been a primary research focus for C/C composites [1-4,6-9]. As a result, reliable short-term oxidation protection for several hours, and up to about 1500°C is now guaranteed by the combination of a SiC coating and glass crack sealant, but long-term and high temperature resistance is still under active study [4,6]. In addition to this shortcoming, few reliable mechanical design data for C/C composites are available [1-4]. Consequently, intensive projects have been proposed, for example in the United States, Europe, and Japan for the development of reusable space planes using high temperature composites [10,11], but none of the projects has succeeded, partly due to the difficulty dealing with the high temperature materials.

In spite of the above difficulties, owing to this material's excellent performance at high temperatures, development studies are underway on the applications of C/C composites to a turbine disk, heat exchangers, and plug nozzle for a future spacecraft engine, an air-turbo ram-jet with an expander cycle, ATREX, engine [11,12]. This engine has been studied for about 15 years at the Institute of Space and Astronautical Science (Japan) as a suitable candidate for the first stage engine of a two-stage-to-orbit, TSTO, space plane. This engine is expected to have sufficient thrust to attain a flight speed of Mach 6 up to an altitude of 35 km. This is a combined cycle engine performing like a turbojet up to Mach 2 flight and a fan-boost ramjet up to Mach 6. Figure 1 shows the schematics of the ATREX engine under development along with its temperature environments. The main features of this engine include the utilization of hydrogen fuel, adoption of an expander cycle to improve high speed capability, and the employment of high temperature composites, especially C/C composites. In

the present paper, the design concepts of the turbine disk, heat exchanger, and plug nozzle for the ATREX engine using 3D-C/C composites and the difficulties encountered in its developmental studies are reviewed.

Fig.1 Schematic drawing illustrating the mechanism of an air-turbo ram-jet engine for use in a future Japanese space vehicle and its temperature environment.

2 CARBON-CARBON COMPOSITES

In addition to their superior mechanical performance at high temperatures, C/C composites have several advantages over other materials, though the C/C composites have a serious drawback of extremely low oxidation resistance. For the turbine application, their low density, low thermal expansion coefficient, and high thermal conductivity are also useful properties regarding thermal stress reduction and the prevention of thermal shock damage. The thermo-mechanical properties of carbon-carbon composites are briefly summarized below for the convenience of later discussion.

2.1 Mechanical Properties

The tensile strength of C/C composites generally increase with increasing temperatures up to about 2500°C as shown in Figure 2 [3,13], although Young's modulus gradually decreases from about 1500°C. This tendency was also confirmed in other strength, shear and compressive strengths and fracture toughness [14,15]. Hence, we can conservatively estimate the applicability of C/C composites to high temperature structures based on their room temperature properties. The strength of the C/C composite shown in this figure is not high enough for use in the turbine disk of the ATREX engine. For this application, a high strength of about 700 MPa is required for a C/C to guarantee sufficient reliability. The tensile strength of C/C composites is known to be primarily controlled by the strength of fiber/matrix interfaces [16]. By lowering the interfacial strength, the tensile strength of three-dimensionally reinforced C/C composites, 3D-C/Cs, can easily attain the above value [17]. However, it should be noted in the design of C/C structures that the interfacial degradation simultaneously leads to low compressive strength [18] and low shear strength [19].

Extremely low shear strength is a well-known drawback of C/C composites [20,21]. In particular, interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) is about one-tenth of that of fiber-reinforced plastics; the ILSSs of unidirectional and cross-ply CC composites have been reported to be 20~30 MPa and 10~20 MPa, respectively [14,15,20]. In their applications to the turbine disk, heat exchangers, and nozzle, complex tri-axial stress distributions are anticipated. In order to avoid premature shear damage, three-dimensionally reinforced, 3D-C/Cs were chosen for ATREX applications [22]. An additional advantage of the 3D-C/Cs is that their fracture toughness is extremely high compared with 2-dimensionally, 2D, reinforced C/Cs [23]. This high toughness is derived from the lower interfacial strength of 3D-C/Cs than that of 2D-C/Cs [24]. Even 2D-C/Cs exhibit notch insensitivity to some extent [21,]. Thus, complete notch insensitivity can be expected for 3D-C/Cs [23].

2.2 Thermal Properties

The advantages of C/C composites also reside in their high thermal conductivity [3,25] and low coefficients of thermal expansion (CTEs) [3]. A typical CTE of a C/C composite in the axial direction of the fiber ranges from -1.5 to 0×10^{-6} 1/K at room temperature. This low CTE of C/C composites is maintained at temperatures over 2000°C. When the C/C composites are joined with other materials, such as metals, this extremely low CTE causes a huge thermal mismatch strain. The thermal conductivity of C/C composites varies considerably depending on the quality of the carbon fiber

[3,25]. The highest conductivity can be obtained using pitch-based fibers with high heat-treatment temperatures. Conventional C/C composites have intermediate conductivity [15], which is nearly the same as a carbon fiber reinforced polymer matrix composites. However, the highest conductivity of C/C composites is much higher than that of high conductivity metals. These excellent thermal properties make C/Cs highly resistant to thermal shock [3].

2.3 High Temperature Oxidation

The most serious problem encountered in C/C composites is their low oxidation resistance. In order to improve their oxidation resistance, a coating is often applied on the surfaces of C/Cs. Figure 3 [8] compares the mass loss rates of bare and SiC-coated C/C composites.

As this figure shows, the SiC-coating considerably lowers the mass loss rate of the C/C composite. However, this improvement is not sufficient for the ATREX application. The coating on a C/C composite is usually applied at an elevated temperature, exceeding 1000 °C. Thus, during cooling from the coating treatment temperature to room temperature, many cracks appear in the coating due to thermal mismatch strains between a coating material and the C/C composite [8,9]. Through these cracks, oxidation still proceeds. Hence, a glass-based material is usually over-coated on a ceramic coating to seal the cracks [26]. A silicon carbide, SiC, coating over-coated with vitreous crack sealant is now believed to be most promising. However, it is useful only over short periods and in a temperature range up to about 1700°C [6,8] due to evaporation of the glass sealant. The glass crack sealant should be liquid in a temperature range suitable for oxidation protection, because the coating cracks vary in width with temperature. Owing to this requirement, the evaporation temperature of the glass sealant inevitably becomes rather low [26]. Consequently, complete suppression of oxygen ingress by diffusion through the coating cracks in a long term is extremely difficult even at rather low temperatures [6]. The SiC coating is oxidized to form a thin, stable SiO₂ film on the coating surface at a temperature range lower than 1700°C under atmospheric pressure. However, over 1700°C, "active oxidation" occurs in the SiC coating under atmospheric pressure, as shown in the left hand side of Figure 3, where the SiC coating continuously evaporates in the form of gas phase SiO [9].

The turbine disk should be protected against hydrogen at temperatures under 1500 °C. The reaction rate of hydrogen with carbon or SiC is about 10² to 10³ times lower than that of oxidation [27]. Thus, the SiC coating is sufficient for a short time usage of the turbine disk.

Fig.2 Temperature dependence of tensile strength in a cross-ply-laminated C/C composite obtained under a vacuum up to 2273 K and an Ar atmosphere over it [13].

Fig.3 Mass loss rates, dW/dt , of bare and SiC-coated C/C composites due to oxidation.

3 TURBINE DISK

3.1 Design of Turbine Disk

The tip-turbine structure to be formed using a 3D-C/C has a shape shown in Figure 4. Since C/C composites are the only materials that have superior mechanical properties at temperatures higher than 1500°C [1-3], the utilization of C/C composites is regarded as an indispensable factor to attain a flight speed of Mach 6. At this speed, the turbine disk rotated up to 440m/s, and the strength required for a C/C composite at this maximum speed has been estimated to be 350 MPa. Since the high stress caused by centrifugal force in the disk is induced only in the circumferential direction [22], a high volume fraction of reinforcing fiber should be loaded in this direction. A tensile strength higher than

800MPa was confirmed to be attainable using a 3D-C/C having fiber volume fractions in x , y , and z directions, 40%, 10 %, and 5% [17]. Thus, using a r - θ - z reinforced 3D-C/C disk, we can easily satisfy this strength requirement.

Fig.4 A tip turbine structure for the burst ATREX engine.

Fig.5 A schematic drawing of the spin tester and fracture detection set-up.

3.2 High Speed Rotation Tests

High speed rotation tests have been carried out to explore problems associated with high speed rotation. Another aim of the rotation tests was to clarify the vibration behavior related to rotational imbalance inherent to the C/C disks. Figure 5 represents a schematic illustration of the utilized rotation burst tester driven by air turbines, which has a maximum rotation speed of 100,000 r.p.m. In this tester, telemeters and cameras are installed to measure strain distributions and to take photographs of fracture initiation in rotating disks, respectively. During rotation tests, the test chamber was evacuated by a rotary pump.

(a)Joined structure (b)Monolithic structure (c)Fly-out behavior (d) 3D C/C after fracture

Fig.6 Simplified models of a turbine disk made of 3-dimensionally reinforced C/C composites.

The rotational tests were carried out on various annular C/C disks having different reinforcing patterns, 2D or 3D reinforcement, varying ratios of inner and outer diameters, and various notch lengths. These tests verified that the fracture criteria established by static tests are also applicable to the disk even in rotational burst tests [28], and that the required rotational speed for the ATREX application is attainable using a 3D-C/C [29]. Typical model disks made of 3D-C/Cs are shown in Figure 6.

During the rotation burst tests of the 3D-C/C disks, micro-fractures and the resulting fragment fly-outs were observed at much lower rotational speeds than that of the total fracture [29,30]. A large number of the fragment fly-outs induced vibration due to rotational imbalance of the disk [30], which is fatally harmful to the ATREX engine. The clearance between the blade tips and shroud should be set lower than 0.2 mm for production of high rotational power. Vibration of large amplitude might make the blades come in contact with the shroud and result in fracture of the blades. This type of sever micro-fractures was not observed in 2D-C/C discs. This is due to the coarse fiber texture adopted in the 3D-C/Cs (using thicker fiber bundles; 12,000 to 36,000 filament/bundle) compared with 2D C/Cs and their tendency to possess weaker bundle interfaces [40,42]. Detailed discussion of this fly-out behavior is given in reference [29], which includes analysis and effective measures to prevent the fly-out phenomenon.

4. HEAT EXCHANGERS

4.1 Design and Processing

According to a preliminary calculation, a heat exchange area of 10 m^2 is required to effectively operate the expander cycle in a 40 mm diameter ATREX model [11,12]. To realize this large heat exchange area, in addition to a conventional insert-type exchanger, the walls of the combustion chamber and the plug nozzle were determined to be utilized for heat exchangers. The wall type and the insert type heat exchanger now under discussion are schematically shown in Figures 7 (a) and (b), respectively. Since heat resistance beyond $1500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is partly required for the materials used in the heat exchangers, C/C composites are experimentally applied in high temperature regions. The primary difficulty in these applications is how to form 3D-C/Cs into the complex shapes of the heat exchanger. The hydrogen gas within the ducts of the heat exchangers possesses a maximum pressure of 40 atm, whereas inside and outside of the combustion chamber, combustion gas and air have pressures of 10 and 1 atm, respectively. Hence, the duct walls and combustion chamber must sustain a maximum pressure difference of 39 atm at a temperature of 1500°C .

Fig.7 Heat exchangers made of C/C composites under development.

The heat exchanger formed in the wall of the combustion chamber is composed of a cylinder containing many duct holes and manifolds, and is fabricated by the processes shown in Figure 8.

This heat exchanger is made of a r - θ - z -reinforced 3D-C/C with fiber volume fractions of $V_{f-r}=20\%$, $V_{f-\theta}=20\%$, $V_{f-z}=3\%$. The manifolds are mounted at the inlet and outlet portions of the combustion chamber. They distribute the fuel H_2 to the ducts of the heat exchanger, and gather and send it to the turbine. In the preform of the combustion chamber shown in Figure 8 (1), 90 copper tubes with a outer diameter of 5 mm were inserted to form the ducts for the hydrogen flow. Copper tubes were used because copper does not chemically react with carbon even at elevated temperatures. The copper tubes were set at 3 mm distances from the free surfaces in order to satisfy the required gas leakage level of 3 %. This preform was fabricated first by piercing CFRP rods of 0.8 mm diameter on a thickly polyurethane-coated mandrel, and then placing θ and z fiber bundles between the pierced rods using filament winding technique. The preform was then infiltrated with phenolic resin, followed by carbonization of the resin at $650 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The resultant porous 3D-C/C was densified by 4 cycles of hot isostatic pressing until achieving a density of 1.45 g/cm^3 . The HIP treatment was performed at a low temperature of $650 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in order to avoid melting and large deformation of the Cu tubes. The density of 1.45 g/cm^3 might be too low for structural application, but this density is convenient for a Si infiltration treatment for the prevention of gas leakage. This treatment will be discussed later. Next, the copper tubes were chemically dissolved with nitric acid. The resulting 3D-C/C was then heat-treated at $2000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and carbon-bonded to the manifold.

- The above-mentioned process has been completed. The next process shown in Figure 8 (6) is Si infiltration into the 3D-C/C. This process is aimed at the minimization of gas leakage through the exchanger and is performed at $1600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The infiltrated Si almost completely occupies the space of open defects in the 3D-C/C and chemically reacts with carbon in the 3D-C/C to form SiC. Finally, a SiC coating and vitreous over-coat is to be applied on the surfaces of the chamber to prevent oxidation of the 3D-C/C. The glass over-coat evaporates easily, so that the over-coating should be treated periodically after a pre-determined operation time [26].

Cu tubes
 ϕ 5 x 90

Temperature
< 1273 K

- (1) r-q-z 3D carbon fiber preformed with Cu tubes. (2) Densification of carbon matrix by HIP method. (3) Remove Cu tubes by nitric acid. (4) Heat treatment at 2273 K.

Fig.8 Schematic drawings illustrating a fabrication process of a wall-type heat exchanger.

4.2 Key Technologies

In addition to design and fabrication technologies, there exist several key technologies which must be established for the production of the heat exchangers. These topics will be briefly reviewed below.

4.2.1. Bonding. The bonding between C/C composites is to be used, for example, between the wall-type heat exchanger and the manifold. The heat exchangers are to be used at high temperatures. Thus, high temperature capability is also required of the bonding material. As a bonding material, carbon and SiC were examined. Carbon bonding is expected to have a high temperature capability exceeding 2000 °C, and SiC bonding is expected to result in stronger bonding.

Carbon bonding was performed by the procedure shown in Figure 9. The bonding strength between cross ply C/Cs was evaluated by means of the double-notched compression method. Figure 10 shows the bonding strength and interlaminar strength of the substrate C/C as a function of temperature. As this figure shows, bonding strength as well as interlaminar strength is enhanced with temperature increase. The principal factor for this improvement was shown to be the evaporation of absorbed water [31], and this effect was generally observed in carbon materials [32].

SiC bonding has a strength of 20-30 MPa, and it has been already confirmed that the bonding strength also improved with temperature increase [33]. Thus, SiC bonding is useful especially in the case in which high bonding strength is required. SiC bonding was executed by placing a Si sheet between polished C/C plates under a pressure of 10MPa at 1600 °C. Under elevated temperatures, Si reacted with carbon in the C/C plates to form SiC. The pressure required at high temperature limits the applicability of SiC bonding. As an alternative method, the following two-step procedure was examined; 1) C/Cs were bonded by carbon, 2) the carbon-bonded C/C was impregnated with Si. This process can be executed without simultaneous application of pressure and high temperature. This method was shown to be effective not only in obtaining high bonding strength but also in the minimization of gas leakage through the bonding layer.

Fig.9 An explanatory diagram of the resin-carbonization-bonding process.

Fig.10 Temperature dependence of bonding strength between C/C composites using carbon adhesive and interlaminar shear strength of the C/C composite.

4.2.2. Oxidation. Recently, the authors have developed a new concept regarding the coating deposited on C/C composites [34], which involves a multi-layered SiC/carbon coating composed of sub-micron-thick layers. It is well known that when the coating becomes thinner than a critical value, coating cracks are suppressed [34,35]. The concept advanced by the present authors involves the alternate stacking of two coating materials with thicknesses lower than the critical values. In this coating, one of the coating materials has to be of a large critical thickness. In the present case, carbon has a critical thickness of about 6 μm . Coating cracks can, then, be completely eliminated as demonstrated in Figures 11 (a) and (b), where the white layers are SiC and the black layers are carbon [34]. Note that the substrate C/Cs in these photographs are inclined in order to enlarge the CTE of the substrate in the in-plane direction. In the case of figure (a), each coating thickness is thinner than the critical values, but in case (b) the SiC layers are thicker than the critical value. A $\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4/\text{BN}$ multi-layered coating is under development for application to the heat exchangers. Silicon nitride and boron nitride were chosen for this coating, because the critical thickness of the Si_3N_4 , $> 1 \mu\text{m}$, is estimated to be much thicker than that of SiC, 0.2 μm , and BN is more oxidation-resistant than carbon.

•••(a) $\theta=36^\circ$ (b) $\theta=38^\circ$
Fig.11 Cross-sectional views of SiC/C multi-layered coatings applied on unidirectionally reinforced C/C substrates inclined the fiber direction in order to change thermal expansion in the horizontal direction.

4.2.3. Gas leakage. C/C composites usually include plenty of pores and cracks as shown in Figure 12 (a) for a cross-ply laminated C/C. Thus, gas easily passes through C/Cs if no countermeasures are adapted. The ATREX system requires a heat exchanger leakage of less than 3 % of the total hydrogen gas [11,12]. However, non-treated C/Cs leak a greater amount of gasses than that. Gas leakage occurs mainly through open pores and cracks. Thus, the gas leak rate strongly depends on the micro-structure of the composites. To prevent gas leakage, two counter-measures were examined. The first examined was Si infiltration into pores and cracks in a C/C composite [36]. This treatment was performed at 1600°C, and most of the impregnated Si was converted to SiC with volumetric expansion [35-37]. The pores and cracks are then almost sealed, though small cracks are newly formed, as shown in Figure 12 (b). By this treatment, the gas leak rate was lowered by three orders of magnitude and became lower than that for the ATREX requirement for a 3 mm C/C plate, as shown in Figure 13 [38]. Exploring further improvements, a refractory metal, Ni, was thinly plated on the surface of the C/C. The Ni coatings were applied using two procedures, electro- and electroless processes, indicated in the figure by Ni-plating and electroless Ni, respectively. The electro-plated Ni tended to include large pin-holes, but electroless plating did not. Thus, electroless plating completely

suppressed the leakage. However, the electroless plating is effective under low temperature environments less than 1000°C and under low-pressure differences. When the pressure difference between the both surfaces becomes high, the plating tends to debond from the substrate C/C due to the pressure. Similar leakage problems have been recently discussed by several authors but in different situations [39], for example in the development of a hydrogen rocket tank for use at cryogenic temperatures.

••••• (a) Bare-C/C (0°/90°) •••••••••• (b) Si impregnated C/C (0°/90°)

Fig.12 Cross sections of C/C with cross ply lamination before (a) and after Si infiltration (b).

Fig.13 Nitrogen gas leak rates of various cross-ply laminated-C/Cs (2D-C/Cs) as a function of gas pressure.

5. PLUG NOZZLE

Figure 14(a) schematically shows the plug nozzle for the ATREX engine. This nozzle is connected to the combustion chamber at the cowl. The plug is supported by the two struts. The combustion gas flows through the space between the plug and the cowl & mobile skirt. The movement of the skirt makes an optimum outlet gap, which varies with flight speed and altitude (environmental pressure). The temperature of the sharp end of the mobile skirt is estimated to be higher than 2000 °C due to high temperature gas flow. This region is cooled by gas flow supplied by the 45 holes of 3 mm in diameter.

Fig.14 A schematic drawing of the plug nozzle and A schematic drawing illustrating the reinforcing pattern of the struts. Thick short lines represent thin rods for the reinforcement in the thickness direction. The rods are made of carbon fiber reinforced phenolic resin matrix composite.

The cowl and the mobile skirt were fabricated using 3D-C/Cs. The holes for the ejection of cooling gas were formed using the Cu resolving technique employed in the wall-type heat exchanger. The 3D-preforms for struts and plug are now being fabricated. Near net shape 3D-preforms of the struts are difficult to weave. Consequently, the struts were determined to be divided into simple elements, as shown in Figure 14(b) which can be formed with 2-dimensional in-plane reinforcement by, for example, the filament winding process. All the elements thus formed are then arranged into the final shape. Finally, thin CFRP rods were pierced in order to join the elements and to reinforce them in the thickness direction, as schematically illustrated in the right hand figure.

6. CONCLUDING REMARKS

For the last 10 years, the present authors have been investigating C/C composites, with the aim of applying C/C composites to components of the ATREX engine. This feasibility study on C/C composites summarized the recent results of the authors and their coworkers. This ATREX engine project includes not only the turbine disk, heat exchangers, and plug nozzle discussed here, but also the air-intake and miscellaneous components. This project is determined to be scaled-up and the construction of more realistic small scale models made of C/C composites will officially start in the fiscal year 2003. Though these goals constitute great challenges, their achievements will provide valuable information regarding the practical applications of high temperature composite materials in severe environments.

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